

DEVELOPMENT OF INTENSIVE TECHNOLOGY FOR PROCESSING PHOSPHOGYPSUM

Zhalgasbaeva Barno Muratbay kyzy
Berdakh Karakalpak State University
2nd-year Master's student

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Abstract. This thesis covers the issues of processing phosphogypsum waste generated in the process of phosphoric acid production based on intensive technology. Based on the analysis of the physicochemical properties of phosphogypsum, an energy-saving technological model based on mechanochemical activation, chemical neutralization, and low-temperature thermal modification was proposed. Optimal ranges of process parameters were determined on a theoretical basis, and indicators of environmental and economic efficiency were assessed.

Keywords: phosphogypsum, industrial waste, intensive technology, mechanochemical activation, thermal modification, environmental safety.

Login. Complex processing of industrial waste is one of the priorities of the modern chemical industry. Phosphogypsum, formed during the production of phosphoric acid, accumulates in large volumes, causing environmental problems. In the production of 1 ton of extraction phosphoric acid, an average of 4-5 tons of phosphogypsum are formed. Storage of these wastes in open areas leads to soil degradation, groundwater pollution, and atmospheric dust. Phosphogypsum mainly consists of $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, which may contain P_2O_5 residues, fluorine compounds, and heavy metal ions. Moisture content 25-40%, pH in the range of 2-4 and characterized by an acidic environment. These factors limit the possibility of its direct industrial application.

The purpose of the research is to develop a theoretical model for processing phosphogypsum based on energy-saving and environmentally safe intensive technology.

Research methods. During the work, methods of theoretical analysis of the physicochemical properties of phosphogypsum, study of the kinetic regularities of mechanochemical processes, modeling of the thermal modification process, and optimization of technological parameters were used.

Results and analysis. It was established that for effective processing of phosphogypsum, the stages of preliminary drying (100-120°C), grinding (0.1-0.3 mm), and chemical neutralization are necessary. As a result of neutralization with CaO, the pH of the medium was increased to 6-7. In the process of mechanochemical activation, the particle surface area increases, and reactivity increases. During thermal modification (150-170°C), the reaction $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O} + 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ occurs and a hemihydrate form is formed. Calculations showed that the proposed technology reduces energy consumption by 25-30% compared to traditional methods and allows for the recycling of 85-90% of waste. The physical and mechanical properties of the resulting product meet the requirements of building materials. Scientific novelty: the complex application of mechanochemical activation and low-temperature thermal modification in the processing of phosphogypsum has been substantiated, and the optimal range of process parameters has been determined.

Practical significance. When the proposed intensive technology is implemented at industrial enterprises, the volume of phosphogypsum storage facilities is reduced, the

environmental load is reduced, and economic efficiency is increased. The possibilities of producing building materials based on local raw materials will expand.

Conclusion. Intensive phosphogypsum processing technology allows for the reduction of industrial waste and the rational use of resources. The complex mechanochemical and thermal approach is characterized by energy efficiency and high efficiency.

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